

ANALYSIS OF CORED WIRE COMPONENTS FOR WELDING AND MELTING COATING.

Ruziboyev Javoxir Shokirjon o'g'li

Andijan Machine building institute

Master of the Specialty "Welding production technology and equipment"

javohirruziboyev05215@gmail.com, +998932550205

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Abstract. This article talks about the areas of use of cored wires, the components that make up its components.

Key words: cored wire, shell, core, gas generator, slag generator, oxygen scavengers, stabilizer, alloying.

The powder wire is a continuous electrode, consisting of a metal sheath and a powder core (powder filler) inside it.

Figure 1. Cored wire.

For most of the wires designed to weld and melt steel, alloys and cast iron, a cold - rolled 0.2-0.8 mm thick strip of low-carbon steel with a high degree of plasticity necessary for wire formation and stretching serves as a shell. A strip of metal with a suitable composition is used in the preparation of powdery Wire for melting and welding of non-ferrous metals [1]. The core of the wire consists of an alloy of minerals, ores, metals, ferrocoats and other substances powders that ensure that the welding process is stable and stable and that compounds with the required use descriptions are formed. According to its function, the components of the core are divided into gas-forming, slag-forming, stabilizing and stabilizing materials, oxygen purifiers, as well as special additives. Many materials perform several tasks during the welding process [2]. Gas-forming materials serve to create a gas phase in the welding zone, which absorbs air from the surface of the phase welding bath and protects liquid metal from harmful gases (nitrogen, hydrogen) from the point of view of metallurgy.

Alkaline and alkaline earth metals carbonates (marble, magnesium, dehydrated soda), organic substances (cellulose, starch, wood flour) are used as gas-forming materials. Slag-forming materials are added to form a welding slag, which ensures that the weld seam in particular forms well by performing metallurgical and technical tasks. Salts of metals and their minerals and ores (rutile, kremenem, glynosem, alumosilicates, marble, magnesium, etc.), fluorides and oxides of alkali metals are slag-forming materials. Active metals that are very close to oxygen are used as oxygen cleaners (raskisliteli). These metals are added to the core in the form of ferroalloys (ferromanganese, ferrosilicon, ferrotitanium, etc.) and metal powders [3].

Ferroalloys and metal powders (ferrochromium, ferrotungsten, ferrovanadium, chromium, molybdenum, nickel, etc.) Allowing tasks are also performed by materials - oxygen scavengers [4].

Stabilizing materials are designed to ensure stable and stable arc combustion in a wide range of welding modes. For this purpose, compounds of elements with low ionization potential are used, which, as a rule, are found in gas-forming and (or) slag-forming materials [5].

Special additives serve to indirectly influence the welding or melt coating process in addition to the coating. As such additives, corrosion inhibitors (to protect against the rust of the metal organizers of the wire), iron powder are used. Iron powder is a mandatory component of most powdery wires, since it participates in the formation of a welded seam, increases the productivity of the process [6].

In general powder wire grooves can be classified into five types according to their composition: rutile-organic, carobnate-fluorite (basic), fluorite, rutile, and rutile-fluorite [7].

In the preparation of powder wire, not only the composition of its core is determined, but also the optimal design of its section is selected. For powder-coated wire, a simple shell structure is used: tubular or tubular [8].

Powdered wires are used for welding and fusion coating without shielding the weld pool or with additional shielding with gas or flux. Wires that do not require additional protection are called self-shielding wires, in which the protection of metal by gas and slag is carried out due to the separation (dissociation) and melting of gas-forming and slag-forming materials in them.

Before starting welding or fusion coating, it is necessary to heat the powder wire in the modes indicated in the normative or technological documents [9].

Many, especially powder welding wires, can be used in mechanized and automated welding processes. Welding and welding with wires of most brands is carried out using reverse polarity direct current. Welding and fusion coating when using powder wires productivity of work increases by 1.5-4 times compared to manual work [10].

Conclusion. For powder welding wires, the class of the metal to be welded, the method of protection used, the possibility of using it in welding in different spatial situations, the guaranteed indicators of the mechanical properties of the melt-coated metal are the most important. Powder coating wires are primarily classified according to the chemical composition of the coating metal and the function of coating.

Powder welding and fusion coating wires are classified according to such indicators as the type of core, process productivity, welding-technological characteristics, hygienic characteristics. The requirements for these and some other indicators are defined in the wire standards and specifications.

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